

Comparative Study among Kirkuk University Students on Oral Health Knowledge and Attitudes

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Abstract

Background: Dental and pharmacy students are at the frontline of patient contact, so they need to be role models to their patients and communities about oral health and oral care, which is closely linked to the development of many dental and systemic diseases.

Aim of the study: To assess the self-reported dental and oral health behaviours of Iraqi dental and pharmacy students in Kirkuk Governorate, Iraq.

Subjects and Methods: A cross-sectional questionnaire-based study involving 300 participants, 178 dental students and 122 pharmacy students in their final year at the university. Hard copies of the questionnaire were distributed and included questions to assess their knowledge, attitudes and practices in various oral health topics. Frequency analysis and chi-square tests were then used to determine the differences between the dental and pharmacy students on the topics in question.

Results: The positive responses to questions in all three domains showed a significant positive difference in favour of the dental students in 25 out of 29 questions. 89% of the dental students recognised the relationship between oral health and general health, whereas 70% of the pharmacy students shared this awareness (p -value=0.000). Dental students excelled in understanding the purpose of tooth brushing, with 96% recognising its role in preventing tooth decay and gum disease, whereas 73% of the pharmacy students recognised this relationship (p -value=0.000).

Conclusions: Dental students outperformed pharmacy students in their knowledge, attitudes and practices related to oral health.

Introduction

Health behaviours are the activities that individuals undertake to protect, improve or maintain their well-being and to prevent disease [1]. Oral health problems are associated with several systemic diseases [2]. Therefore, the maintenance of overall well-being requires the collaboration of health care professionals (HCPs), including medical and dental professionals as well as pharmacists [3]. Dental students (DS) are seen as potential providers of oral health care. Therefore, they should act as role models for their relatives, contacts and patients. The self-care routines and behaviours of DS have a significant impact on improving the oral health of their patients and also play a role in

promoting public awareness of oral health education [4]. Therefore, it is suggested that comprehensive preventive care programmes for undergraduate dental students should be included in the same framework [5]. This will enable them to empower patients towards oral self-care and enhance their expertise. These efforts should enable future dentists to promote health behaviours that are independent of individual characteristics [6]. Research suggests that dental students (DS) demonstrate different levels of oral health knowledge and behaviours at different stages of their dental education, particularly during the clinical and preclinical years, as oral health attitudes and behaviours tend to improve during the clinical years of

More Information

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training compared to the preclinical years [6]. Dental students' oral health attitudes and behaviours also vary between countries and cultures [7, 8]. Pharmacists, and potentially pharmacy students (PS), are seen as key contributors to the provision of health care and well-being in the community. Pharmacists have an advantage in understanding the needs of community members because of their regular contact with patients. In certain geographical areas, pharmacists are often the first point of contact for patients and, in certain cases, they are the only healthcare professionals with whom patients interact [9, 10]. It is therefore important to assess the current state of their understanding and behaviour in relation to oral health [11]. Pharmacists are able to provide oral health information at the request of patients, and a minority of pharmacists actively provide this information without being asked. Most pharmacists believe that providing oral health information is part of their profession. In addition, those who do not have access to dental care and those from disadvantaged socio-economic backgrounds are more likely to seek advice from pharmacists on oral health issues [12]. A survey of pharmacists revealed that they receive at least one enquiry per week about oral health problems. Approximately 50% of these enquiries were specifically related to oral lesions or ulcers [12]. Pharmacists provided oral health advice and expressed a desire to develop their expertise in this area as the need for such advice is expected to increase in the future [13]. Few studies are known to discuss the oral health knowledge, attitudes and practices of Iraqi dental and pharmacy students. This study aims to assess the self-reported dental and oral health behaviours of Iraqi dental and pharmacy students in Kirkuk city.

Methods

Study Design

A questionnaire based cross-sectional study involving final year students of Dentistry and Pharmacy at the University, a hard copy of the questionnaire was printed and distributed to randomly selected classes of final year students of both were asked to submit their responses due to a pre-determined deadline, a total of 300 valid responses were received and the data from these responses were analysed.

Questionnaire components and scoring criteria

The authors developed a questionnaire adapted from previous studies [14], with modifications to the questions to suit the scope of the current work. The students' demographic data, including age and gender, were collected, followed by three sections: the first section included questions to assess students' knowledge of various oral health topics, the second section included questions to assess differences in dental hygiene practices and attitudes between students, and the third section focused on their

attitudes towards oral care practices. The responses from the hard copies were collected in an Excel spreadsheet for further testing.

Study Settings

The study was conducted at both the College of Dentistry and the College of Pharmacy under the supervision of the authorities at the College of Dentistry. The distribution of the questionnaire took place on 12 November 2023 and the subjects were asked to submit their answers by 1 December 2023. The subjects' consent to share their responses to participate in the study was obtained and included as part of the paper copy of the questionnaire.

Participants

Inclusion Criteria

Dentistry and pharmacy students of both sexes were in their final year of undergraduate study at the university.

Exclusion Criteria

Students who did not agree to share their answers and forms submitted after the deadline.

Sample Size Estimation

A convenient sampling technique was used to determine the sample size for this study, resulting in 300 valid responses that were used for testing in the current study.

Statistical Analysis

Data analysis, including descriptive and inferential analysis, was carried out using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences® (SPSS), version 25.0. Frequencies and percentages of DS and PS with positive and negative responses were also obtained. A chi-square test was used to determine the difference between the knowledge, attitudes and practices of dental students and pharmacy students regarding oral health. P = 0.05 was used as the level of statistical significance.

Results

Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants

A total of 300 participants were included, consisting of 178 DS and 122 PS. The female to male ratio is almost 1.1:1. Table 1 summarises the demographic characteristics.

Table 1: Demographic Data of the Participants

Demographic Factor	Dental	Pharmacy	Total
Gender			
Male	85	58	143
Female	93	64	157
Age by Years			
23 - 25 years old	178	122	300
Academic Year			
Final year	178	122	300

Knowledge of Dental and Pharmacy Students on Oral Health Topics

When assessing the understanding of the relationship between oral health and general health, it is evident that DS has the highest level of awareness with 89% recognising this relationship, while PS has a lower level of awareness at 70%. A similar pattern is observed when considering the purpose of tooth brushing, with 96% of DS recognising its role in preventing tooth decay and gum disease (p-value= 0.000). Furthermore, there is a significant difference between the two groups in recognising the appropriate hardness of the toothbrush, with DS recognising 88% and PS 74% (p-value= 0.002). DS have more knowledge about the preventive potential of brushing twice a day with fluoridated toothpaste, with 87% acknowledging this fact compared to 75% of PS (p-value= 0.009). In terms of oral hygiene practices, DS have a better understanding of flossing (83%) compared to PS (p-values= 0.003) and they are also more likely to understand the recommended frequency of flossing compared to PS. Similarly, DS are more aware of the existence of different types of dental floss, with 81% aware (p-value= 0.009).

In addition, DS are better at recognising common dental conditions such as caries and gingivitis, with 92% awareness compared to 62% for PS. They also show greater awareness of the main cause of these conditions, plaque, with 88% recognising this fact

compared to only 49% of PS (p-values= 0.000). Furthermore, DS show a strong awareness of the detrimental effects of sugary foods on dental health, with 96% recognising their harmful effects compared to 83% of PS. Similarly, DS excel in understanding the indicators of dental caries, with 93% recognising that the presence of a cavity indicates this condition, compared to 72% of PS (p-values= 0.000).

In addition, DS show a superior understanding of gingival bleeding with 77% awareness compared to 54% for PS. They also outperformed their counterparts in recognising methods to prevent gingival bleeding, with 76% awareness (p-values= 0.000).

DS are also more aware of the effects of soft drinks on teeth, with 84% recognising their negative effects, compared to 54% of PS. They are also more familiar with the concept of bad breath, with 82% recognising it. DS also excel in understanding the causes of halitosis, with 83% awareness comp (p-values= 0.000). DS show superior knowledge of chronic trauma and its association with oral cancer, with 74% awareness. They also have a better understanding of the link between smoking and qat chewing and oral cancer, with 85% recognising this link compared to 54%. In addition, DS are more likely to recognise the condition of stomatitis, with 85% awareness (p-value= 0.000). Table 2 provides further details of positive responses to oral health questions for DS and PS.

Table 2: Knowledge of Students Regarding Oral Health

University Students (n) %			
Question	Dental	Pharmacy	*p-Value
Oral health and general health	(158) 89	(85) 70	0.000
Purpose of tooth brushing to prevent tooth decay and gum disease	(171) 96	(89) 73	0.000
What kind of toothbrush hardness is suitable for healthy people?	(157) 88	(90) 74	0.002
Dental caries can be prevented by brushing with fluoridated toothpaste twice daily	(155) 87	(91) 75	0.009
Knowledge regarding dental flossing	(148) 83	(83) 68	0.003
How often should we floss our teeth?	(144) 81	(82) 67	0.009
Do you know that there are different types of dental floss to be used?	(144) 81	(82) 67	0.009
Two most common dental diseases (Dental caries & gingivitis)	(164) 92	(76) 62	0.000
Main cause of dental caries and gingivitis (plaque)	(157) 88	(60) 49	0.000
Role of sugary foods in dental caries (harmful effect of sugar to teeth)	(171) 96	(101) 83	0.000
Presence of cavity indicates dental caries	(166) 93	(88) 72	0.000
Knowledge about gingival bleeding	(137) 77	(66) 54	0.000
Methods to prevent gingival bleeding	(135) 76	(63) 52	0.000
Effect of soft drinks on teeth	(150) 84	(66) 54	0.000
Do you have any idea about halitosis?	(146) 82	(54) 44	0.000
Cause of halitosis	(148) 83	(52) 43	0.000
Chronic trauma and oral cancer	(132) 74	(56) 46	0.000
Relation of smoking & Qat chewing with oral cancer	(151) 85	(66) 54	0.000
Do you know what is stomatitis?	(151) 85	(56) 46	0.000

Disparities in Dental Hygiene Attitudes Among University Students

When considering the necessity of morning and evening brushing, DS showed the highest level of awareness with 88.2% recognising the importance of this practice. Similarly, when assessing the necessity of rinsing after meals, DS (78.6%) maintained a higher level of awareness compared to PS (p-value= 0.000). Furthermore, regarding the need for annual dental check-ups, DS again showed the highest level of awareness, with 88.2% acknowledging the importance

of these check-ups, compared to 64.8% of PS (p-value= 0.000). Regarding the link between sugary foods and tooth decay, a significant majority of all students recognise this link, with DS leading with 96.1%, followed by 77.9% of PS (p-value= 0.000). Finally, when examining the belief that fluoride toothpaste strengthens teeth, the DS again show the highest awareness, with 84.3% agreeing with this view, while 70.5% of the PS share this belief (p-value = 0.012). Table 3 shows the level of agreement between DS and PS regarding dental hygiene practices.

Table 3: University Students' Agreement Level Regarding Dental Hygiene Practices

Question	University Students (n) %		
	Dental	Pharmacy	*p-value
Question 1: Necessity of Morning and Night Brushing			
- Yes	(157) 88.2%	(84) 69.0%	0.000
- No	(13) 7.3%	(8) 6.5%	
- Don't know	(8) 4.5%	(30) 24.5%	
Question 2: Necessity of Rinsing After Meals			
- Yes	(140) 78.6%	(79) 64.8%	0.000
- No	(10) 5.6%	(27) 22.1%	
- Don't know	(28) 15.8%	(16) 13.1%	
Question 3: Necessity of Yearly Dental Checkup			
- Yes	(157) 88.2%	(79) 64.8%	0.000
- No	(14) 7.8%	(20) 16.4%	
- Don't know	(7) 4%	(23) 18.8%	
Question 4: Sugary Food and Tooth Decay Relationship			
- Yes	(171) 96.1%	(95) 77.9 %	0.000
- No	(3) 1.7%	(12) 9.8%	
- Don't know	(4) 2.2%	(15) 12.3%	
Question 5: Fluoride Toothpaste Strengthen teeth			
- Yes	(150) 84.3%	(86) 70.5%	0.012
- No	(13) 7.3%	(13) 10.6%	
- Don't know	(15) 8.4%	(23) 18.9%	

Oral Care Practices of Students

When examining the frequency of routine dental check-ups, 68% of DS and 60.7% of PS reported regular check-ups (p-value= 0.218), as shown in Figure 3.

There were no significant differences in tooth brushing frequency between the study groups. DS were more likely to brush their teeth twice a day (53.4%), while PS (40.1%) were less likely to brush their teeth twice a day (p= 0.091). Among those who never brush their teeth, 10.6% and 14.8% of DS and PS, respectively, never brush their teeth. In comparison, 27% of DS and 29.5% of PS brush their teeth only once a day. In addition, 9% of DS and 15.6% of PS brush their teeth three times a day, as shown in Figure 4. The use of fluoride toothpaste showed that DS had the highest use rate (88.8%), followed by PS (75.4%) (p-value= 0.006), with DS more likely to use fluoride toothpaste. Regarding the frequency of toothbrush replacement, the majority

of students in all fields reported changing their toothbrush every 3 months, 68% of DS and 63.1% of PS (p-value= 0.852). On the other hand, 16.9% of DS and 18.9% of PS change their toothbrush every 6 to 12 months.

In addition, 9.5% of DS and 11.5% of PS changed their toothbrush after one year. However, only 5.6% of DS and 6.5% of PS changed their toothbrush until the bristles frayed, as shown in Figure 5. When considering different oral hygiene aids, 35.4% of DS use mouthwash and 32.6% use dental floss compared to 41% and 27% of PS respectively. 20.2% of DS use siwak compared to 18.9% of PS. Those who never use oral hygiene aids account for 11.8% and 13.1% of DS and PS respectively (p-value= 0.682). Figure 6 shows the different distribution and specialisation of oral hygiene aids. Table 4 shows the comparison of oral care practices between DS and PS.

Table 4: Oral Care Practices of Students

University Students (n) %			
Practice	Dental	Pharmacy	*p-value
Routine Dental Check-ups			
Yes	(121) 68%	(74) 60.7%	0.218
No	(57) 32%	(48) 39.3%	
How many times in a day you brush your teeth?			
Never	(19) 10.6%	(18) 14.8%	0.091
Once	(48) 27%	(36) 29.5%	
Twice	(95) 53.4%	(49) 40.1%	
Thrice	(16) 9%	(19) 15.6%	
Using Fluoride-containing toothpaste			
Yes	(158) 88.8%	(92) 75.4%	0.006
No	(15) 8.4%	(26) 21.3%	
Don't know	(5) 2.8%	(4) 3.3%	
Frequency of changing brush			
Every 3 months	(121) 68 %	(77) 63.1%	0.852
Every 6–12 months	(30) 16.9%	(23) 18.9%	
After one year	(17) 9.5%	(14) 11.5%	
Until the bristles fray	(10) 5.6%	(8) 6.5%	
Different oral hygiene aids			
Mouthwash	(63) 35.4%	(50) 41%	0.682
Dental floss	(58) 32.6%	(33) 27%	
Siwak	(36) 20.2%	(23) 18.9%	
None	(21) 11.8%	(16) 13.1%	

Discussion

Health care is an integrated practice that requires advice and guidance for different requests from different health professionals. DS and PS play an important role in health care systems, especially in the knowledge of oral health and its importance among the general public [15]. As future health care providers, they need to have a high level of awareness of self oral health care so that this attitude can be instilled in patients and the community at large [16, 17]. The results of this comprehensive study show significant differences in several aspects of oral health knowledge, attitudes and practices between dental and pharmacy students in Kirkuk. These differences highlight the importance of a tailored oral health education curriculum and interdisciplinary collaboration to improve the overall oral health knowledge, attitudes and practices of future health professionals. Data analysis in the knowledge section revealed that DS were more informed about oral health compared to PS. DS' knowledge of oral health topics is largely acquired from their curriculum during their five years at dental school. In contrast, the lack of oral health knowledge among PS could be attributed to the absence of similar courses in their curriculum [15]. These findings are consistent with previous studies that have reported similar results [16, 18-22]. In addition, several factors may have contributed to the low positive response of

the PS, such as the lack of education and training in oral health or the limited interaction between them and the dental students. A similar finding of poor oral health knowledge has been reported among PS from Malaysia [23, 24]. DS consistently demonstrated the highest level of awareness of various aspects of oral health knowledge. This is consistent with previous studies conducted by Kumar H et al, Rong WS et al, Al-Batayneh et al, Saran et al, and Al Kawas et al, who also found that DS had a deeper understanding of oral health, and other studies found that PS had lower levels of oral health knowledge [16, 17, 20, 25, 26]. Previous studies conducted by Hajizamani HR et al. and Baseer MA to assess oral health knowledge among PS found that they had an intermediate level of oral health knowledge [27, 28]. In this study, in terms of knowledge differences, 89% of DS recognised the relationship between oral health and general health, while 70% of PS shared this awareness. The high percentage of DS who reported knowledge of the relationship between oral health and general health may be due to the fact that dental students receive specialised training focused on oral health, which includes a deep understanding of the oral-systemic health relationship in their curriculum. Previous studies by Usman et al and Pradhan et al support this finding. This shows that the role of oral health is part of overall health [29, 30]. The knowledge of appropriate toothbrush stiffness for healthy

individuals is consistent with a previous study by Kumar H et al, although their study specifically compared medical and dental students [16]. In this study, which included PS instead of medical students, no significant difference was observed between the two groups of students. Specifically, 88% of DS and 74% of PS demonstrated knowledge of this topic. These results suggest that there is a difference in understanding between these student categories when it comes to selecting the correct toothbrush firmness for individuals without specific dental problems. In addition, 87% of DS agreed with the use of fluoridated toothpaste twice daily to prevent tooth decay, compared to 75% of PS. These findings were similar to those reported by Kumar et al, Cebeci et al and Ahmed et al, who found that 82%, 79% and 81% of DS respectively agreed that caries could be prevented by brushing with fluoridated toothpaste [16, 19, 31, 32]. In terms of oral hygiene knowledge, DS showed significantly superior knowledge, especially in the area of dental flossing. Dental flossing is just as important as toothbrushing for cleaning teeth. A striking 83% of DS showed awareness of flossing, whereas PS lagged behind with 68% of them showing awareness. Previous studies have shown much lower awareness of flossing among DS, with 32% and 16% showing awareness. This may be due to a lack of education about the benefits of flossing [16, 33]. Furthermore, DS showed a remarkable understanding of common dental diseases, including dental caries and gingivitis, with 92% awareness, which is similar to what Kumar H found about DS knowledge of common dental diseases, which was 88% [16]. In stark contrast, PS lagged behind with 62% awareness. In addition, DS were more informed about the harmful effects of sugary foods on dental health, with an impressive 96% recognising the harmful effects of sugar, compared to 83% for PS, which is less than the percentage of PS (98%) who answered positively to the question linking sugar consumption with tooth decay in a study conducted by Rajiah K [24]. This finding is consistent with the wider literature, which highlights an increased awareness of the role of diet in oral health among DS [34, 35]. DS also showed increased awareness of the negative effects of soft drinks on teeth, with 84% recognising the negative effects. In contrast, only 54% of PS shared this awareness. This finding is consistent with previous studies indicating that DS have a better understanding of the impact of dietary choices on oral health [19, 34, 35]. In addition, DS showed a higher level of familiarity with the concept of halitosis, with 82% recognising it, compared to 44% of PS. They also excelled in understanding the causes of halitosis. The finding that PS were the least likely group to answer this question positively is in line with another study that examined pharmacy students' knowledge of oral health and found that "among the six knowledge

questions, the question (Do you know what halitosis is?) was the least correctly answered question, with only 18.9% of students answering it correctly" [24]. In addition, dental students demonstrated superior knowledge of chronic trauma and its association with oral cancer, with 74% awareness compared to 46% among pharmacy students. This finding is consistent with existing research, which emphasises that DS generally have a heightened awareness of the link between chronic trauma and oral cancer [16]. When asked about their knowledge of smoking and qat chewing as causes of oral cancer, DS showed a much higher positive response. They also had a greater understanding of the link between smoking and Qat chewing and oral cancer, with 85% recognising this link, compared to PS.

This is consistent with the findings of Kumar et al, Ahmed et al, Frola and Barrios, who emphasised that dental students generally have a heightened awareness of the association between smoking and oral cancer [16, 32, 36]. In the present study, in terms of attitudinal differences, PS showed negative attitudes and inadequate self-care practices towards oral health. It can be speculated that the average oral health knowledge of pharmacists may be the main reason for such a finding [37]. The majority of DS showed an increased awareness of the need for morning and night tooth brushing, with 88.2% recognising the importance of this practice and agreeing with the need to brush their teeth in the morning and at night to keep them healthy. This finding is consistent with previous research that has highlighted the importance dental students place on proper oral hygiene practices [16, 17, 20, 25, 26]. In contrast, PS, although still aware, showed a comparatively lower level of recognition of the importance of this routine. For example, only 69% of PS responded positively to the need for morning and night brushing, which is higher than a similar study by Baseer MA et al, who found that only 23% brushed in the morning and at night [28].

Similarly, DS showed considerable understanding of the importance of rinsing the mouth with water after meals to remove accumulated food particles. Although PS also showed awareness of this practice, DS maintained a significantly higher level of awareness. However, few participants either disagreed or were unaware of this attitude, perhaps preferring to brush their teeth rather than rinse with water after meals for better oral health. These findings were similar to those of Aljrais MM et al [15]. In addition, DS again showed increased awareness of the need for annual dental check-ups, with 88.2% confirming the importance of routine check-ups at dental clinics for preventive measures, which may be the result of the medical orientation of dental students during their training programme and concern for their oral health. Conversely, PS acknowledged the

importance of such check-ups but showed a lower level of awareness. This observation is partly consistent with previous research on DS and PS by Aljrais MM et al, who found that 92% of dental students agreed with routine dental visits, while 88% of PS also agreed with this attitude [15, 34]. Many studies support these findings [38-40]. When students were asked about sweets and sugary foods as a cause of tooth decay, a significant majority of all students across all disciplines recognised the link between the consumption of sugary foods and tooth decay. However, DS led the way with an impressive 96.1% recognising the link. PS, while still demonstrating awareness, reported a lower percentage of recognition at 77.9%. This reflects that it is a common and obvious fact, as sugary foods are known to contribute to tooth decay. These findings were higher than those of Aljrais MM et al, who found that 66% of DS and 70% of PS appreciated this relationship [15]. Finally, DS showed a remarkable level of awareness (84.3%) regarding the belief that fluoride toothpaste strengthens teeth. This is consistent with the results of studies by Aljrais MM et al, who found 92%, Kumar H, who found 82%, Cebeci et al, who found 79%, and Ahamed et al, who found 81% among DS [15, 16, 31, 32]. In contrast, PS, while still showing awareness of the concept, reported a lower percentage of 70.5%. Aljrais MM et al found that 93% of PS agreed with this concept. This suggests that the majority of DS and many of PS were aware of the benefits of fluoride toothpaste in strengthening teeth and preventing dental caries. In terms of oral care practices, it is noteworthy that DS and PS were very similar in terms of regular dental check-ups among university students. DS had the highest rate of regular check-ups, followed by PS. DS showed a greater propensity for routine check-ups compared to their peers in the pharmacy programmes. This reflects an average practice rate for oral health care, as the majority of the two study groups show almost equal percentages, indicating that students are concerned about their oral health care as a preventative measure. A similar result was found by Aljrais MM et al in their study who found that 40% of DS and PS performed routine dental check-ups twice a year, although the result was also not statistically significant [15]. The frequency of tooth brushing showed small differences between the two study groups. DS were significantly more likely to brush twice a day (53.4%), while PS (40.1%) were less likely to brush twice a day. The difference between the two groups suggests better oral hygiene practices among the DS. A higher percentage (74%) of DS brushing twice a day was reported by Neeraja et al [41]. Other studies showed a higher percentage of DS with 77% and 85% brushing their teeth twice [16, 19]. Another study by Benjamin et al. showed that 27.5% of DS brushed their teeth twice a day, which is much lower than the percentage

observed in the current study [42]. On the other hand, 27% of DS and 29.5% of PS brushed their teeth only once a day. Similar studies have shown this lower proportion of DS brushing only once at 31% [3]. In addition, the use of fluoride toothpaste is highest among DS, followed by PS. These differences show that DS are more likely to choose fluoride toothpaste as part of their oral care routine. The benefits of fluoride toothpaste are taught in the curriculum of dental and pharmacy schools. A previous study by Aljrais et al. found that 60% of DS and 65% of PS used fluoride toothpaste, but the result showed no significant differences between the two groups [15]. Conversely, when asked about the frequency of toothbrush replacement, the majority of students in all fields reported adherence to the recommended practice of changing their toothbrush every 3 months, with DS at 68% and PS at 63.1%. This finding suggests a consistent commitment to a key aspect of oral hygiene across all disciplines. There were significant differences in the use of oral hygiene aids. DS showed a higher propensity to use mouthwash (35.4%) and dental floss (32.6%) compared to their pharmacy college counterparts at 41% and 27% respectively. In addition, the use of siwak was more prevalent among DS (20.2%) compared to PS (18.9%). These differences highlight the potential influence of discipline-specific training on students' choice of additional oral care tools.

Study limitations

The main weakness of this study is its cross-sectional nature and the potential bias introduced by the physical handling of hard copies of the questionnaire.

Conclusions

Dental students (DS) have superior knowledge and attitudes towards oral health and hygiene topics compared to pharmacy students (PS). This may call for the development of pharmacy student programmes to include oral health topics.

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